

On the Averaging of the Electromagnetic Field in Metasurface Modeling

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Abstract – In this work, we present a fully numerical modeling technique for 2D-periodic composite electromagnetic structures known as metasurfaces. Utilizing the field-flux eigenmode Finite Element formulation, we outline the treatment of the general eigenvalue problem pertaining to metasurfaces. Subsequently, we propose an averaging process of the associated electromagnetic fields at paths prescribed by the Generalized Sheet Transition Conditions. Average field components of a metasurface consisting of split-ring resonators are illustrated and discussed.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parameter retrieval of metamaterials using a combined eigenvalue analysis and field averaging was recently proposed in [1], where the structure's intrinsic behavior is revealed via the return of the dispersion diagrams and the microscopic field distributions of the modes supported by the composite medium. The process of substituting the rapidly varying (microscopic) electromagnetic fields of resonant structures periodic in three dimensions with average values was thoroughly discussed there, and in several other works in the literature [2, 3].

In this work, we demonstrate the proper eigenvalue treatment of metasurfaces and propose their corresponding field averaging procedure. Taking outset in the eigenvalue treatment of a single unit cell of the metasurface, we extract the corresponding dispersion diagrams of a structure consisting of the periodic arrangement of edge-coupled split-ring resonators (EC-SRRs). We subsequently propose a field averaging procedure appropriate for such metasurfaces which is based on the Generalized Sheet Transition Conditions (GSTCs).

II. FINITE ELEMENT MODELING OF METASURFACES

We utilize the $\mathbf{E} - \mathbf{B}$ Bloch-Floquet FEM formulation to simulate a periodic metasurface consisting of EC-SRRs arranged on an orthogonal lattice [4, 5, 6]. The solution of this formulation returns both the electric intensity \mathbf{E} and the magnetic induction \mathbf{B} at the same order of approximation, a feature that will be of importance in the field averaging process described in section III. The unit cell of this composite structure is illustrated in Fig. 1a. We assume that the resonators are $17 \mu\text{m}$ thick, made of copper (conductivity $\sigma = 5.8 \cdot 10^7 \text{ S/m}$), and embedded in free space. A rectangular (xyz) coordinate system is introduced such that the resonators are located in the xy -plane. To simulate a metasurface, periodic boundary conditions are imposed on the xz and yz boundaries, while Absorbing Boundary Condition of the 1st order terminates the computational domain at the xy boundary.

The normal component of the electric field (E_z) for the supported mode at 5 GHz is illustrated in Fig. 1b, exactly above and below the metasurface. A sign change is observed, which implies the existence of a surface electric charge distribution in the electrostatic limit [5, 7]. By a quick comparison with the results for the corresponding 3D-periodic metamaterial in [7], it is observed that the metasurface mode reported in Fig. 1b resembles completely the one reported in this reference. The dispersion diagrams for the two in-plane components of the wave vector k_x and k_y corresponding to orthogonal angles of incidence are shown in Figs. 2a and 2b, respectively. It is easily observed that the behavior of the structure is similar in both incidence cases, with respect to the returned eigenmodes: For frequencies up to 8.1 GHz and from 8.5 GHz and above, the metasurface supports the returned surface modes (hybrid polariton modes [7]), whereas there is a bandgap between 8.1 and 8.5 GHz, inside which,

Fig. 1: (a) Unit cell of the EC-SRR metasurface and its dimensions in mm. (b) Real part of the E_z component above (left) and below (right) for the supported mode of k_x incidence at 5 GHz.

the modes are extremely evanescent, possessing an attenuation constant larger than 50 dB/m. Conclusively, the overall behavior of the dispersion diagrams for both incidences, along with the distributions of the supported modes exhibit an absolute resemblance compared to the 3D-periodic EC-SRR medium [7].

III. METASURFACE FIELD AVERAGING

The results in Fig. 1b clearly show that the field distributions of the supported modes exhibit very fast spatial fluctuations in regions close to the scatterers. As already mentioned in [1], the calculation of macroscopic, average field quantities of a structure's supported mode is feasible as far as the guided wavelength is much larger than the dimension of its unit cell and there is no evidence of higher order Bloch-Floquet modes. What is, therefore, sought in this context, is the substitution of the microscopic, spatially-varying field quantities returned from the numerical solution with unique, average values, that account for the interaction of the fields with a homogenized structure. For the corresponding metamaterial based on EC-SRRs, the field averaging technique was thoroughly analyzed in [1]. There, the tangentially continuous field components were averaged on the edges and the face-medians of the unit cell (line integrals), whereas the normally continuous fields were averaged on its facets (surface integrals). The specific choice of the averaging paths was made on the basis of the effective constitutive parameters of the metamaterial along with Maxwell's equations on integral form.

In this work, however, we turn our attention to an appropriate averaging technique for the presently investigated metasurface consisting of EC-SRRs, i.e., a structure that lacks periodicity along its normal axis. To this end, use is made of Generalized Sheet Transition Conditions (GSTCs) which have turned out to be appropriate for the characterization of metasurfaces. In the framework of GSTCs, the boundary conditions that connect the electromagnetic fields above and below the metasurface with the electric, magnetic and possible magnetoelectric surface susceptibilities $\bar{\chi}_{ee}$, $\bar{\chi}_{mm}$, $\bar{\chi}_{em}$ and $\bar{\chi}_{me}$, respectively, take on the following mathematical form [8, 9]:

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\mathbf{H}_+ - \mathbf{H}_-) = j\omega(\epsilon_0 \bar{\chi}_{ee} \mathbf{E}_t + (1/c_0) \bar{\chi}_{em} \mathbf{H}_t) - \hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \nabla_t([\bar{\chi}_{mm} \mathbf{H}]_z), \quad (1a)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}} \times (\mathbf{E}_+ - \mathbf{E}_-) = -j\omega(\mu_0 \bar{\chi}_{mm} \mathbf{H}_t + c_0 \epsilon_0 \bar{\chi}_{me} \mathbf{E}_t) - \hat{\mathbf{n}} \times \nabla_t([\bar{\chi}_{ee} \mathbf{E}]_z), \quad (1b)$$

where \mathbf{E}_+ , \mathbf{E}_- are the electric fields above and below the metasurface, \mathbf{H}_+ , \mathbf{H}_- are the corresponding magnetic fields and $\mathbf{E}_t = (\mathbf{E}_+ + \mathbf{E}_-)/2$ and $\mathbf{H}_t = (\mathbf{H}_+ + \mathbf{H}_-)/2$.

We note that these equations indicate the paths where the appropriate field averaging may be conducted in the case of a composite metasurface structure. Therefore, we propose that the integration of the microscopic electric and magnetic field on the surfaces is done exactly above and below the resonators inside the unit cell. For example, the x component of the electric and magnetic field may be, respectively, obtained as

$$\mathbf{E}_{av,x} = \frac{1}{S_{xy}} \iint_{S_{xy}} \mathbf{E} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}} dS_{xy}, \quad \mathbf{H}_{av,x} = \frac{1}{S_{xy}} \iint_{S_{xy}} \mathbf{H} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}} dS_{xy}. \quad (2)$$

We emphasize that the magnetic field \mathbf{H} is obtained from the magnetic induction \mathbf{B} , via the constitutive relation $\mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \mu_r \mathbf{H}$. In this way, it maintains its order of approximation, without requiring any differentiation, as it would be the case if evaluated by Faraday's law, in single-variable FEM formulations existing in the literature.

In Figs. 2c and 2d we illustrate the dominant electric and magnetic average field components corresponding to the EC-SRR metasurface for both in-plane incidences. A similar behavior is observed for both field components at both incidences ($E_{y,ave}$, $H_{z,ave}$ for k_x and $E_{x,ave}$, $H_{z,ave}$ for k_y incidence, respectively), whereas their returned results corresponding to the upper and lower surfaces of the metasurface appear to be very close in absolute values.

Fig. 2: (a) Real and (b) imaginary part of the complex propagation constant of the EC-SRR metasurface for k_x and k_y incidence (c) Average electric field and (d) average magnetic field, above and below the metasurface for both in-plane incidences.

Comparing these results to a 3D-periodic EC-SRR metamaterial from [1], we conclude that the dominant field components coincide for both incidences, along with their overall behavior around the resonance frequencies.

IV. CONCLUSION

A full-wave numerical treatment of metasurfaces was presented in this work. The treatment was based on the field-flux eigenmode formulation that was combined with the Generalized Sheet Transition Conditions in order to obtain the final average fields. The method was illustrated through an investigation of an EC-SRR metasurface. In addition to the dispersion diagram, which displayed the expected behavior, its average fields were obtained through integrations of the obtained microscopic fields along appropriate surfaces above and below the metasurface. The final results show the suitability of the proposed method for metasurface modeling. The next steps will involve determination of the homogenized metasurface parameters, as well as the application of the proposed characterization technique for a wide range of metasurfaces.

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Nitas and T. V. Yioultis, "Electromagnetic parameter retrieval technique utilizing eigenvalue analysis and field averaging," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 131, pp. 11 (114902), Mar. 2022.
- [2] D. R. Smith and J. B. Pendry, "Homogenization of metamaterials by field averaging," *JOSA B*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 391-403, Mar. 2006.
- [3] V. V. Gozhenko, A. K. Amert, and K. W. Whites, "Homogenization of periodic metamaterials by field averaging over unit cell boundaries: use and limitations," *New J. Phys.*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 043030, Apr. 2013.
- [4] V. Salonikios, M. Nitas, S. Raptis and T. V. Yioultis, "Computational Analysis of Graphene-Based Periodic Structures via a Three-Dimensional Field-Flux Eigenmode Finite Element Formulation," *PIER*, vol. 92, pp. 157-167, May 2020.
- [5] M. Nitas *et al.*, "Numerical Calculation of Dispersion Diagrams and Field Distributions of Waves in 3-D Periodic Split-Ring Resonator Media," *IEEE Trans. Magn.*, vol. 55, no. 12, pp. 1-4, Dec. 2019.
- [6] C. Fietz, Y. Urzhumov, and G. Shvets, "Complex k band diagrams of 3D metamaterial/photonic crystals," *Opt. Express*, vol. 19, no. 20, pp. 19027-19041, Sep. 2011.
- [7] M. Nitas and T. V. Yioultis, "Characterization of edge-coupled broadside-coupled and complementary split-ring resonator periodic media based on numerical solutions of eigenvalue problems," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 69, no. 12, pp. 5259-5269, Oct. 2021.
- [8] K. Achouri, M. A. Salem, and C. Caloz, "General metasurface synthesis based on susceptibility tensors," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 63, no. 7, pp. 2977-2991, Jul. 2015.
- [9] E.F. Kuester, M.A. Mohamed, M. Piket-May and C.L. Holloway, "Averaged transition conditions for electromagnetic fields at a metafilm," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 51, no. 20, pp. 2641-2651, Oct. 2003.